

INFORMATION STORAGE AND RETRIEVAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ADOPTED BY SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES FOR SUCCESSFUL BUSINESS OPERATIONS IN EBONYI STATE

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Abstract: *The study was carried out to ascertain information storage and retrieval management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 2,433 small and medium scale enterprises in Ebonyi State, whose businesses were registered with the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria. The sample size of 344 small and medium scale enterprises was used for the study. A structured questionnaire containing 29 items entitled “Information Storage and Retrieval Management Practices Adopted by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (ISRMPASEQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three (3) experts. The Cronbach Alpha Reliability coefficient was 0.92. Three hundred and forty four (344) copies of instrument were distributed, while 321 copies representing 93% were successfully retrieved from the respondents. Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) were used for finding answers to the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistical tool. The findings showed that information storage and retrieval management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State are filing of documents, saving in diskette, recording in a register, saving in a computer hard disc, storing in a file cabinet, saving in a tape recorder, recording in business diary and storing in flash drive are the information storage practices is adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations and printing from diskette, printing from computer hard disk, checking filed document, reading of previous minutes, reading newspapers, magazine among others, checking file cabinet, and printing from flash drive are information retrieval practices*

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adopted by small and medium scale enterprises. The hypotheses tested showed that years of experiences and location of small and medium scale enterprises operators did not differs significantly in their mean responses on information storage and retrieval management practices management adopted by small and medium enterprise in Ebonyi State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended, among others, that small and medium scale enterprises owners should embark on computer training on the application of information storage management practices in order to be able to store their information in the cloud.

Introduction

In today's fast paced digital landscape, effective information management is crucial for the survival and growth of small and medium scale enterprises. Small and medium enterprises are vital to the economic development, contributing significantly to employment, innovation, and Gross Domestic product (GDP). It occupies a significant position in the economic development of every nation, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Since the rise in their popularity, small and medium scales enterprises have consistently grown and generated interest from a wide range of stakeholders including governments, researchers, donors and non-governmental organizations because of their roles in tackling the employment challenges, stimulating innovations and advancement and achieving sustainable Development (World Bank, 2020). As a result, both the developed and the developing countries are actively engaged in and continue to seek pragmatic ways of improving the activities of small and medium scale enterprises.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in Igwe, Oduma and Utebor (2024) defined small and

medium scale enterprises (SMEs) as entities with assets base of N5m and not more than N500M excluding land and buildings with employees between 11 and 200. Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN, 2022) categorized small scale enterprises as business ventures with a minimum of 10 and maximum of 49 employees with assets within the range of five to fifty million Naira (excluding land and buildings), while medium scale enterprises are business ventures with employee number of between 50 and 199; while asset base (excluding land and building) is put at between N50 million and N500 million. In this study, Small scale and medium scale enterprises are business organizations set-up by individuals or group of individuals, known as business operators, for the main purpose of providing goods and services. The capital to operate the business is supplied by only one person or by a few people who are the managers of the business. It is usually a sole proprietorship, a partnership, or a family owned company. Small scale and medium scale enterprises, according to Olufemi (2017), exist in the form of sole proprietorship and partnership, though some could be

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registered as limited liability companies and characterized by: simple management structure, informal employer/employee relationship, labour intensive operation, and simple technology, fusion of ownership and management and limited access to capital. Their classification into small and medium enterprises depends on the scale or size of business operators' control.

In Ebonyi State, the small and medium scale enterprises have continued to thrive even before the creation of the state in 1996. About 80% of all the economic activities in Ebonyi State are purely small and medium scale enterprises (Nwusolor, 2016). This accounts for their (SMEs) huge contributions to the greater outputs of the Ebonyi State economy. According to SMEDAN (2022) collaborative National Survey of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), Ebonyi State has 2,433 small and medium scale enterprises. They bring employment generation, poverty reduction and diversification of the economy among others, these small and medium scale enterprises are located in different strategic positions of the State (Ebonyi) especially in the capital territory (Abakaliki). They operate in different dimensions as water production, cassava processing, rice milling, provision stores, hair dressing, fruit juice making, computer centers, shoe making, palm oil production, vehicle repairs and maintenance, laundry and dry cleaning services, bookshops, transport service/companies, carpentry, electronics

repairs and accessories, poultry farms, restaurants and fast food centers, saloons (haircuts/plaiting), fruits and vegetable vendors, cosmetics shops, among others. These enterprises have been struggling resiliently to survive on their own even when the State Government has not shown enough interest to promote them. To a reasonable extent they have contributed immensely to the economic growth of the State.

Though small scale and medium scale enterprises are making positive contributions to economic growth and development in Ebonyi State, the rate of failure is high. According to West and Wood in Nwsolor (2016), 90 percent of all these business failures result from lack of experience and knowledge about the Information management practices. Information management practices refer to the policies, procedures, and technologies used to collect, store, protect, retrieve, share, and dispose of information. Information management allows small and medium scale enterprises operators to achieve various goals. It improves compliance, reduces risk and controls access to vital business information. An effective information management system can help small and medium scale enterprises operators control the creation and growth of records. A great information management system can improve how small and medium scale enterprises operators store and retrieve information required during their daily activities. It can also make it easier to

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disseminate information to diverse recipients via multiple channels, allowing teams to collaborate and communicate easily across time zones and locations. An effective information management practices can help the small and medium scale enterprises operators extract actionable insights from its records to guide them in decision-making. Information management practices also helps small and medium scale enterprises operators create a reliable institutional memory and use it for planning and making important strategic decisions. Small and medium scale enterprises operators need a process to safeguard their vital information from competitors and unauthorized access. Information management provides a system for protecting proprietary information from intruders, system failures and natural disasters. It helps protect the confidentiality and integrity of vital information assets, allowing the owner to derive maximum benefits from their trade secrets. Umar and Umar (2021) stated that the key area of information management in the business environment (which small and medium scale enterprises need to adopt) include information storage practice, and information retrieval practices as the basis for better business decisions and for improved productivity.

Information storage management practices refer to the method, techniques, and strategies used to collect, organize, and maintain information in a structured and accessible manner. Information storage practices are the

retention of information using technology specifically developed to keep information and make it as accessible as necessary. Information storage refers to the use of recording media to retain data using computers or other devices. The most prevalent forms of data storage are file storage, block storage, and object storage, with each being ideal for different purposes. Jackie (2019) noted that information storage practices are a critical business resource and like any other critical resources must be properly managed. by Shehu (2019) noted that small and medium scale enterprises can store their information in file, saving in diskette, recording in a register, storing in fax paper roll, storing in a metallic plates, saving in computer hard discs, storing in file cabinets, saving in a tape recorders, recoding in business diary and storing in flash drives. Storage is used in small and medium scale enterprises, data centers, edge environments, remote locations and people's homes. O'Brien (2022) opined that storage facilities are very important for the success of small and medium scale enterprises managers. Nkuma and Adebajo (2021) stated that small and medium scale business owners need information storage facilities in order to keep relevant business information for quality decision making. Sigler (2019) agreed that managers of small and medium scale enterprises need storage facilities to preserve information and is one of the most common data storage approaches used by small and medium scale enterprises operators to save

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information for decision making. In Ebonyi State there is no available information on the information storage practices adopted by operators of small and medium scale businesses in carrying out their business activities. Small and medium scale enterprises are seen carrying out their business activities without knowing if they adopted good information storage practice. Information retrieval management practices refer to the method of locating, access, and extract relevant information from stored data. Information retrieval, according to Anyaehie (2016), is the science of searching for information within documents, as well as relational databases and the World Wide Web. Information retrieval is the process of searching for relevant documents from an unstructured, large corpus that satisfy the user's information needs. And it is a tool that finds and selects from a collection of items a subset that serves the user's purpose. Roger (2017) added that computer assisted retrieval of microfilm involves the use of a microprocessor for quick retrieval of information. The visual display unit terminals are used to communicate directly with a computer which is able to locate a document filed on advances the film to the correct frame, stops the filling and displays the image of required document on the screen. Thus providing immediate access by visual display unit of information stored on a computer as well as a means of gaining access to original source documents stored on microfilm. It was further found that

interviewing was also a way of retrieving information. Graham (2016) explained that interview can be an excellent source of retrieving information. Similarly, the study of Sigler (2019) explained that at any time, information can be retrieved from the disc by calling it back into memory and displaying it on the screen. The author adds that after a file has been retrieved, it can be edited, revised and printed. Hybels and Weaver (2021) opined that data could be retrieved through the search engines used for accessing the internet. Shehu (2009) emphasized that manually stored information can be retrieved from files, shelves, drawers, among others by going through the documents stored either alphabetically, numerically, chronologically, geographically, among others. In information retrieval systems, the emphasis is on the retrieval of information (not data). This information can be in the form of audio, video, or text, and it is devoted to finding relevant documents, not simple matches to patterns. The effective retrieval of relevant information is directly affected both by the user task and the logical view of the documents. The user task may be information retrieval or information browsing. Classic information retrieval systems (such as web interfaces) normally allow information retrieval alone, while hypertext systems provide quick browsing. Modern digital libraries and web interfaces might attempt to combine these tasks to provide improved retrieval capabilities.

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Experience in business is a factor that may determine the outcome of this study. Experience refers to the knowledge and skills that one gains through doing something for a period of time. Hornby in Ucha (2021) noted that experiences have influence on the way one thinks and behaves. Small and medium-scale business operators have various experiences depending on the years of operation of their businesses. Their years of experience have been organised into two clusters for the purpose of the study. The first cluster is 1–10 years of experience, adjudged by the researcher as lowly experienced, and the second is 11 years and above, adjudged as highly experienced. According to Boden and Nucci (2019), where a business owner has four or more years of experience, the business is more likely to prosper. This may also be connected to the use of information management by small and medium enterprise in Ebonyi State.

Location is another factor that may determine small and medium scale operators' views on the adoption of information management practice in carrying out their businesses. A location is a place where a particular point or object exists. It is also a human settlement: city, town, village, or even archaeological site. Those in rural areas may not boarder to adopt information management because of their location while those in urban area will like to utilized information management because of their area. The reason may be because of the availability of internet facilities in urban and lack of internet

facilities in the rural area. These views, however, are either theoretical in nature or have not been empirically proven to affects small and medium scale business operators utilisation of information management practice in Ebonyi State. It is against this background that the researcher empirically determined the information dissemination and storage management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State.

Statement of the Problem

In today's knowledge –driven economy, effective information storage and retrieval management practices are crucial for the survival and success of small and medium scale enterprises. Effective information storage and retrieval management practices ensure efficient use of storage resources; quick and accurate retrieval of information; data security, integrity, and privacy, compliance with regulations and standard and improved decision making and productivity. The exponential growth of data, coupled with the increasing complexity of business operations, has made it imperative for small and medium scale enterprises to adopt robust information management strategies. Efficient information storage and retrieval enable small and medium scale enterprises to make informed decision, enhance productivity and maintain competitiveness. However, in Ebonyi state, small and medium scale enterprises faces significant challenges in

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effectively managing their information storage and retrieval process, resulting in inefficient data retrieval, increase risk of data loss, theft, and decision making. Furthermore, research conducted by Igwe, Oduma and Utebor (2024) found that 70 percent of small and medium scale enterprises in Ebonyi State lack information management policies, 60 percent experiences data loss or corruption due to inadequate backup systems and 50 report difficulties in retrieving critical information. While extensive research exists on information management in large organizations, small and medium scale specific needs and challenges have received limited attention. This study aims to bridge the gap by investigating the information storage and retrieval practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of this study was to determine the information dissemination and storage management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State. Specifically the study sought determined

1. The information dissemination management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State.
2. The information storage management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State

Research Questions

1. What are the information storage management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operation in Ebonyi State?
2. What are the information retrieval management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operation in Ebonyi State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of small and medium scale enterprises operators regarding information storage management practices adopted by small and medium enterprises in Ebonyi State based on location.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of small and medium scale enterprises operators regarding information retrieval management practices adopted by small and medium enterprises in Ebonyi State based on their years of experience.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 2,433 small and medium scale enterprises in Ebonyi State, whose businesses were registered with the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria. The sample size of 344 small and medium scale enterprises was used for the study. A structured questionnaire containing 29 items entitled

“Information Storage and Retrieval Management Practices Adopted by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (ISRMPASEQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three (3) experts. The Cronbach Alpha Reliability coefficient was 0.92. Three hundred and forty four (344) copies of instrument were distributed, while 321 copies representing 93% were successfully retrieved from the respondents. Mean \bar{x} and Standard

Deviation (SD) were used for finding answers to the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistical tool.

Results

Research Questions One: What are the information storage practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises in Ebonyi State? Data providing answers to research question four is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Information Storage Practices Adopted by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises N=Sample Size

S/N	Item Statement	N	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	Filing of documents	321	3.36	0.72	Agree
2	Saving in diskette	321	3.31	0.78	Agree
3	Recording in a register	321	3.22	0.86	Agree
4	Storing in a fax paper roll	321	1.81	0.91	Disagree
5	Storing in a metallic plate	321	1.65	0.86	Disagree
6	Saving in a computer hard disc	321	3.35	0.72	Agree
7	Storing in a file cabinet	321	3.28	0.73	Agree
8	Saving in a tape recorder	321	2.76	1.10	Agree
9	Storing in cloud	321	1.61	0.79	Disagree
10	Saving in a Google drive	321	2.48	1.08	Disagree
11	Recording in business diary	321	3.34	0.70	Agree
12	Storing in flash drive	321	3.24	0.85	Agree

Data in Table 1 reveal that items 42, 43, 44, 47, 48, 49, 52 and 53 have mean scores between 3.28 and 3.36 which are above the cut-off point of 2.50. They are the storage practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises. On the other hand, items 45, 46, 50 and 51 have mean values of 1.81, 1.65, 1.61 and 2.48 which are below the cut-off point of 2.50 and are not the storage practices adopted by the small and

medium scale enterprises. The small and medium scale enterprises agreed that filing of documents, saving in diskette, recording in a register, saving in a computer hard disc, storing in a file cabinet, saving in a tape recorder, recording in business diary and storing in flash drive are the information storage practices is adopted by small and medium scale enterprises

for successful business operations in Ebonyi State.

Research Questions Two: What are the information retrieval practices adopted by small

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Information Retrieval Practices Adopted by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises for Successful Business Operations

S/N	Item Statement	N	Mean	Std.	Decision
13	Printing from diskette	321	3.38	0.78	Agree
14	Printing from computer hard disk	321	3.31	0.83	Agree
15	playing recorded tape	321	1.76	0.96	Disagree
16	Printing from metallic plate	321	1.72	0.86	Disagree
17	Browsing the Internet	321	1.65	0.81	Disagree
18	Checking filed document	321	3.28	0.82	Agree
19	Reading of previous minutes	321	3.41	0.76	Agree
20	Reading newspapers, magazine among others	321	3.40	0.68	Agree
21	Checking file cabinet	321	3.34	0.75	Agree
22	Printing from flash drive	321	3.24	0.73	Agree
23	Printing from diskette	321	3.36	0.72	Agree

Data in Table 2 reveal that the respondents agreed on eight items (54, 55, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63 and 64) with mean scores between 3.31 and 3.41 which are above the cut-off point of 2.50 as the information retrieval practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises in Ebonyi State and disagree with three items (56, 57 and 58) with mean values of 1.76, 1.72 and 1.65 which are below the cut-off point of 2.50. The respondents agreed that printing from diskette, printing from computer hard disk, checking filed document, reading of previous minutes,

Table 3: Independent t-test of Mean Ratings of Responses of Rural and Urban Small and Medium Scale Enterprises operators regarding Information Processing Management Practices Adopted by small and Medium Scale Enterprises

Items	Location	N	Mean	Std.	Df	t-cal	Alpha	p-val.	Decision
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and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State?

Data providing answers to research question five are presented in Table 2.

reading newspapers, magazine among others, checking file cabinet, and printing from flash drive are information retrieval practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises in Ebonyi State.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in mean responses of small and medium scale operators regarding the information storage management practices adopted by small and medium enterprises successful business operations in Ebonyi State based on location.

Item1	Urban	180	3.40	.69	319	1.23	0.05	.21	Not significant
	Rural	141	3.30	.75					
Item2	Urban	180	3.32	.73	319	.41	0.05	.67	Not significant
	Rural	141	3.29	.85					
Item3	Urban	180	3.22	.83	319	.08	0.05	.93	Not significant
	Rural	141	3.21	.91					
Item4	Urban	180	1.74	.90	319	1.51	0.05	.13	Not significant
	Rural	141	1.90	.93					
Item5	Urban	180	1.65	.84	319	-.02	0.05	.98	Not significant
	Rural	141	1.65	.90					
Item6	Urban	180	3.30	.74	319	-1.30	0.05	.19	Not Significant
	Rural	141	3.41	.68					
Item7	Urban	180	3.28	.79	319	.08	0.05	.93	Not significant
	Rural	141	3.27	.66					
Item8	Urban	180	2.73	1.0	319	-.66	0.05	.50	Not Significant
	Rural	141	2.81	1.13					
Item9	Urban	180	1.63	.81	319	.58	0.05	.56	Not Significant
	Rural	141	1.58	.76					
Item10	Urban	180	2.56	1.07	319	1.56	0.05	.12	Not significant
	Rural	141	2.37	1.09					
Item11	Urban	180	3.33	.72	319	-.19	0.05	.84	Not significant
	Rural	141	3.35	.67					
Item12	Urban	180	3.26	.90	319	.48	0.05	.62	Not Significant
	Rural	141	3.21	.79					
					319	.67	0.05	.56	Not significant

The result of the t-test analyses in Table 3 indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of small and medium scale enterprises operators regarding the information storage management practices adopted by them in Ebonyi State based on location. This is because data in Table 9 show that the p-values for all items (item 42-53) range from 0.12 to 0.93, which are greater than

0.05. The grand P-value 0.560 is greater than 0.05, this implies that the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of small and medium scale enterprises operators on the information storage management practices adopted by small and medium enterprises successful business operations in Ebonyi State based on location is not rejected.

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HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of small and medium scale enterprises operators regarding the information retrieval management practices adopted by

small and medium scale enterprises successful business operations in Ebonyi State based on experience.

Table 4: Independent t-test of Mean Ratings of Responses of Small and Medium Enterprises operators on Information Processing Management Practices adopted by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises for Successful Business Operations Based on Years of Experiences

Items	Gender	N	Mean	Std.	DF	t-cal	Alpha	p-val.	Decision
Item13	0-10years	198	3.36	.80	319	.56	0.05	.57	Not significant
	11years above	123	3.41	.74					
Item14	0-10years	198	3.33	.79	319	.59	0.05	.55	Not significant
	11years above	123	3.27	.88					
Item15	0-10years	198	1.78	.95	319	.58	0.05	.56	Not significant
	11years above	123	1.72	.96					
Item16	0-10years	198	1.74	.88	319	.43	0.05	.66	Not significant
	11years above	123	1.69	.83					
Item17	0-10years	198	1.69	.84	319	1.05	0.05	.29	Not significant
	11years above	123	1.59	.76					
Item18	0-10years	198	3.44	.73	319	4.53	0.05	.00	Significant
	11years above	123	3.03	.90					
Item19	0-10years	198	3.40	.75	319	.15	0.05	.87	Not significant
	11years above	123	3.42	.77					
Item20	0-10years	198	3.40	.66	319	.24	0.05	.81	Not Significant
	11years above	123	3.39	.72					
Item21	0-10years	198	3.33	.72	319	-.22	0.05	.82	Not Significant
	11years above	123	3.35	.82					
Item22	0-10years	198	3.26	.66					

11years above	123	3.21	.83	319	.60	0.05	.54	Not significant
				319	.74	0.05	.54	Not significant

Summary of result in Table 4 indicates that nine (9) out of ten (10) items have their P- values ranging from 0.294 to 0.810 which are greater than 0.05 indicating no significant difference between small and medium scale enterprises operators on the information retrieval management practices adopted for successful business operations in Ebonyi State based on experiences. The grand P-value of 0.54 is greater than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in mean responses of small and medium scale enterprises operators on the information retrieval management practices adopted by small and medium enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State based on experiences is not rejected.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the study showed that the information storage practices adopted by small and medium scale operators for successful business operations include: filing documents, saving in diskette, recording in a register, saving in a computer hard disc, storing in a file cabinet, saving in a tape recorder, recording in business diary and storing in flash drive. This finding relates to the finding of a study by Shehu (2019) who found that small and medium scale enterprises can store their information in file, saving in diskette, recording

in a register, storing in fax paper roll, storing in a metallic plates, saving in computer hard discs, storing in file cabinets, saving in a tape recorders, recoding in business diary and storing in flash drives. Storage is used in small and medium scale enterprises, data centers, edge environments, remote locations and people's homes. The findings are in line with O'Brien (2022) who found that storage facilities are very important for the success of small and medium scale enterprises managers. The findings is in support of Nkuma and Adebajo (2021) who stated that small and medium scale business owners need information storage facilities in order to keep relevant business information for quality decision making. The findings also agree with Sigler (2019) who agreed that managers of small and medium scale enterprises need storage facilities to preserve information and is one of the most common data storage approaches used by small and medium scale enterprises operators to save information for decision making.

The researcher is of the view that the result is so because in business environment, document are always produced and need to be preserved for future. Implementing good database management in small and medium scale enterprises can help owners/managers to keep relevant business information for quality decision making. Furthermore, using storage

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facilities is a good way to keep sensitive information secure and away from potential threats.

However, the test of the fourth hypothesis tested showed that there was no significant difference in mean responses of small and medium scale business operator on information storage management practices adopted by small and medium enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State based on location. This finding is in line with the findings of Sorasalmi and Tuovinen (2016) who found that location of small and medium scale business enterprises may not serve as a pull or push for the utilization of modern information management practices in small and medium scale business enterprises. The findings are in consonance with those of Braesemann, Lehdonvirta and Kassi (2020) that rural small and medium scale operators did not show disproportionate in the use of the modern information management practices compared to those in urban. The findings are in line with a similar investigation conducted by Imai and Malaeb (2017) which found no significant difference in the mean responses of urban and rural small and medium scale business operators on the use of modern information management practices. The findings contradict the findings of Todd (2016) who found that the degree of availability and accessibility of information disseminated through a particular channel depends on the location. For instance, small and medium scale business operators

living in urban areas were more likely to have greater access to information disseminated than small and medium scale business operators living in rural areas in Nigeria. The findings are supported by Baba (2003) who expressed that local populace like the managers of small and medium scale enterprises suffer from low sales, social and economic retrogression due to ignorance and lack of information dissemination of varying types conversely prone business operators to be unaware of current market events and happening in and around them.

The findings of the study also showed how SME operators responded to the information retrieval practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State. The finding revealed that printing from diskettes, printing from computer hard disks, checking filed document, reading of previous minutes, reading newspapers, magazine among others, checking file cabinets, printing from flash drives and printing from diskettes are the only information retrieval management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State.

This finding is in accord with the results of the study conducted by Roger (2017) who added that computer assisted retrieval of microfilm involves the use of a microprocessor for quick retrieval of information. The visual display unit terminals are used to communicate directly

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with a computer which is able to locate a document filed on advances the film to the correct frame, stops the filling and displays the image of required document on the screen. Thus providing immediate access by visual display unit of information stored on a computer as well as a means of gaining access to original source documents stored on microfilm. It was further found that interviewing was also a way of retrieving information. This is in consonance with Graham (2016) who explained that interview can be an excellent source of retrieving information. Graham said that conducting interviews is one of the best ways to gather materials that help in decision making. Similarly, the study of Sigler (2019) explained that at any time, information can be retrieved from the disc by calling it back into memory and displaying it on the screen. The author adds that after a file has been retrieved, it can be edited, revised and printed. This finding agrees with Hybels and Weaver (2021) who opined that data could be retrieved through the search engines used for accessing the internet. This finding is similar to the view of Shehu (2009) who emphasized that manually stored information can be retrieved from files, shelves, drawers, among others by going through the documents stored either alphabetically, numerically, chronologically, geographically, among others. Shehu further stated that electronically stored information can be retrieved by logging into the computer.

The researcher is of the view that the result was so because most SMEs have abundance of information within their company such as customer orders, tender costs, estimation, production scheduling, resource planning among other and retrieval devices are useful for easy location, identification, and trace to the needed information for decision making.

Similarly, the test of null hypothesis 5 showed that there was no significant difference in mean responses of small and medium scale business operators on the information retrieval management practices adopted by small and medium enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State based on experiences. The findings are in agreement with Shaffril and Uli (2018) who found that small and medium scale business operators with working experience of less than 20 years may be willing to switch from the manual system to the electronic system of information retrieval management practices that is made up of the use of modern technologies because such managers are always willing to perform their jobs in an easy and faster way.

Conclusion

This research focused on the information management practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises for successful business operations in Ebonyi State. From the findings of this study, it can be seen that small and medium scale business operators adopted processing, storage and retrieval practices in carrying out their business activities for

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successful business operations in Ebonyi State. Based on hypotheses tested, it is concluded that years of experiences and location of small and medium scale enterprises did not significantly influence the mean responses of operators on information storage and retrieval practices in carrying out their business activities in Ebonyi State. The study concluded that information storage and retrieval practices when properly utilized by small and medium scale enterprises operators will create the required atmosphere for effective functioning of small and medium scale business activities in Ebonyi State and beyond. Increase the performance of small and medium scale business operators towards economic development. Small and medium scale business operators' inability to effectively make use of information storage and retrieval

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practices to carry out business activities has made it difficult for most small and medium scale business operators to survive and make impact in a competitive environment in Ebonyi State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. Small and medium scale enterprises owners should embark on computer training on the application of information storage management practices in order to be able to store their information in the cloud.
2. Government and other bodies serving business people should also consider organizing business training for small and medium scale enterprises on information retrieval strategies for success in business enterprises.

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